

1 **Supplementary Information:**
2 **Effects of phenological mismatch under warming are modified by**
3 **community context**
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6 **Nicholas A. Pardikes^{*1,4}, Tomas Revilla^{1,3}, Chia-Hua Lue^{1,2}, Melanie Thierry^{1,3}, Daniel**
7 **Souto-Vilarós¹, and Jan Hrcek^{1,3}**

8 ¹ Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Entomology, Branisovska 31,
9 37005, Czech Republic

10 ² Biology Department, City University of New York (CUNY), Brooklyn College, 2900 Bedford
11 Ave, Brooklyn, New York 11210, USA

12 ³ University of South Bohemia, Faculty of Science, Branisovska 31, 37005, Czech Republic

13 ⁴ Georgia State University-Perimeter College, Department of Life and Earth Sciences
14 , 55 North Indian Creek Drive, Clarkston, Georgia 30021
15

16
17 Corresponding author: *Nicholas A. Pardikes

18 **Email:** npardikes@gsu.edu
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20 **This PDF file includes:**
21

22 Supplementary text
23 Figures S1 to S11
24 Tables S1 to S16
25 Legends for Datasets S1 to S4
26 SI References
27

28 **Other supplementary materials for this manuscript include the following:**
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30 R-code S1 to S8
31 Datasets used for all statistical analyses
32 Matlab code S1 for dynamic model
33 Additional information about mathematical model used to estimate mortality
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43 **SI Materials and Methods**

44 **Single generation host-parasitoid model**

45 The number of adult flies H_8 and adult wasps I_8 counted on and after day 8 is a function
46 of the initial number of eggs H_0 ($H_0 = 100$ eggs) according to equations

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48 (1) $H_8 = H_0 e^{-8M - 2p}$

49 (2) $I_8 = H_0 e^{-8M - d} (1 - e^{-2p})$

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51 where “e” is the base of natural logarithms, “M” and “d” are mortality rates, “p” is the attack rate
52 by 3 female wasps, and “d” is additional host mortality due to parasitoid handling. Host mortality

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54 (3) $M = m + a H_0/R$

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56 is a function of the number of eggs per volume of food “R”. Parameter “a” is a competition
57 coefficient, and “m” is an intrinsic mortality rate. The parasitoids attack within a window of 2

58 days, hence the “2” instead of “8” in front of “p”. Only the infected host fraction “ $1 - e^{-2p}$ ”

59 experiences additional mortality “d” due to wasp handling.

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61 Empirical mortality rates are calculated using the formula

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63 (4) $\mu = \ln(H_0/H_8)/8$

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65 i.e., the daily rate of geometric decline. Parameters “m” and “a” are estimated by comparing
66 mortality (μ) rates between conditions of low competition ($R = 20$ ml) and high competition ($R =$
67 2 ml), in the absence of parasitoids ($W = 0$). Wasp attack rates “p” are estimated by comparison
68 between mortality (μ) rates, with ($W = 3$; 4-day delay) and without wasps ($W = 0$), for given
69 food level. Experimental replication allowed estimation of expected values and variances for
70 “m”, “a” and “p”. Handling mortality “d” is adjusted by comparison of the number of newborn
71 wasps (parasitoid) against the number of surviving flies (host) of the corresponding experiment
72 without the wasps (i.e., same temperature and food level).

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74 Single generation experiments were simulated by running a day-by-day version of
75 equations (1) & (2) from day 1 to 8, including the effects of environmental and demographic
76 stochasticity. Simulated H_8 and I_8 are then compared with the corresponding (species,
77 temperature, food level, delay) observed numbers of emerged flies and wasps, respectively.

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79 A more detailed explanation for all model equations, parameter estimation, and simulation
80 protocol can be found in the “Model, parameterization & simulations” section at the end of this
81 file.

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83 **Multiple generations host-parasitoid model**

84 Using parameters from the single generation simulations, we projected fly and wasp
85 populations for 100 generations. Starting at generation 0 with 100 fly eggs and 3 female wasps,
86 the number of eggs and females in generation 1 and beyond was obtained with the following
87 recurrence formulas

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89 (5) $H_0' = R_F H_8$

90 (6) $W' = 0.5 S_W I_8$

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92 where H_8 and I_8 follow the stochastic implementation of equations (1) and (2) described at the
93 end of the previous section. R_F is the fly (host) net reproductive ratio, i.e., the expected number
94 of newborn flies that replace a single fly. Host populations with $R_F=1$ or lower are doomed to
95 extinction in closed environments, and the persistence for those with $R_F>1$ is conditional to
96 environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, food level, parasitism). S_W is the wasp (parasitoid)
97 adult survival rate, i.e., the expected probability that an adult fly survives a complete generation
98 and dies. Since only female wasps can parasitize hosts, the contribution of present adults to the
99 next generation is halved by the 0.5 factor (assuming 50:50 female:adult sex ratio for emerging
100 parasitoids). We take care to substitute “p” by “pW/3” because “p” was estimated for $W = 3$
101 females, but now W changes across generations.

102 The combining of equations (1) and (2) with (5) and (6) generates a density-dependent
103 Nicholson-Bailey model. Since the pre-adult phases are simulated stochastically on a daily basis,
104 the model is also age-structured & stochastic. This model is a discrete time model, with discrete
105 generations. It allows us to see the dynamic consequences if delays were maintained over several
106 generations and compare the immediate and long-term expectations. While we recognize this is a
107 tropical host-parasitoid system, this forest still has seasonality with distinct phenologies, thus this
108 still has heuristic value.

109 Parameters R_F and S_W were not obtained from our experimental data. Instead, we set ten
110 different values for each. For $R_F = 1, 2, \dots, 10$. Values equal to 1 or lower always lead to host

111 extinction (see above), thus $R_F = 1$ is a meaningful lower bound. There is no meaningful upper
112 bound for R_F , but we found that $R_F = 10$ is large enough to sustain hosts populations in the
113 absence of wasps. For $S_W = 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1$. Since the lowest possible value of $S_W = 0$ gives trivial
114 results (wasps always go extinct for all conditions), we set the lowest bound at 0.1. The highest
115 bound $S_W = 1$ is of course an ideal condition never to be found even in a laboratory, but it sets
116 upper bounds for long term costs of parasitism, thus we consider this maximum value.

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118 100 replicates for each $100 \times 100 = 10,000$ R_F and S_W combination, and 120 combinations
119 of temperature (24°C, 28°C), food level (20ml, 2ml), host species (*D. Birchii*, *D. Sulfurigaster*,
120 *Sulf-Bir*), wasp species (*Asobara sp.*, *Ganaspis sp.*) and temporal delay (no wasp, 0, 2, 4, 6
121 days), resulted in a total of 1,200,000 simulated timeseries. The simulations were executed in
122 Matlab 2017a. The end of this document shows additional information regarding the model and
123 shows a representative subset of simulations.

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125 **Analysis of observed vs. simulated single generation host-parasitoid model data**

126 After estimation of model parameters “m”, “a” and “p” (means & variances) from the
127 single-generation experiments, we then executed the stochastic version of the model ten times to
128 acquire model estimates of fly and wasp abundance. These simulations over-estimate newborn
129 wasp abundances, and discrepancies with respect to empirical data were used to calibrate
130 parameter “d” (handling mortality).

131 We then used Pearson correlation coefficient to examine accuracy of the model estimates
132 with the observed values of mean abundances of flies and wasps. Correlation coefficients were
133 computed for the entire dataset and among sets of grouped variables of interest (e.g., delay

134 values, temperatures, etc.). To examine which treatments (e.g., delay, competition, temperature,
135 etc.) affected differences between observed and simulated data, we measured the difference
136 between mean observed and simulated values and ran generalized least squared (GLS) models to
137 account for unequal variances across groups, particularly temporal delay periods (Pinheiro *et al.*
138 2017). The difference between observed and simulated data was used as the response variable
139 and temperature, delay, resource competition, species, and wasp species were modeled as
140 predictor variables. We first fit several restricted estimated maximum likelihood (REML) models
141 to identify the best variance-covariance structure within the GLS model to deal with
142 heteroskedasticity. Once a random structure was selected, we compared the fixed effects
143 structure of the model using Maximum Likelihood (ML) and compared models using AICc and
144 likelihood ratio tests (LRT). Type III analysis of deviance (ANOVA) was used to identify
145 significant interactions and main effects within each model. We verified model assumptions by
146 visual inspection of plotted residuals against the fitted values and versus each covariate in the
147 model. All model validation procedures were supported and did not suggest any violations of
148 model assumptions.

149 To identify when observed and simulated values of fly abundance significantly differed
150 from each other, treatments without wasps were used as a control, since differences between
151 observed and simulated fly abundance in those treatments were at or near zero. Similarly, for
152 wasp abundance, our model accurately predicted observed wasp abundances for the zero-day
153 delay window and thus used those values as our control. We used *emmeans* to statistically
154 compare treatments to our predetermined control values and examined which experimental
155 variables caused the difference between the observed and simulated values to deviate
156 significantly from zero (Lenth 2019).

157 The model that minimized AICc for differences between fly abundance allowed the
158 variance to change with temporal delay and included an interaction between resource
159 competition and temporal delay in the fixed effects. For wasp abundance, AICc was minimized
160 when the variance changed with and interaction between temporal delay and resource
161 competition and included an interaction between temperature and host species within the fixed
162 effects.

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164 **Analysis of host-parasitoid dynamic data**

165 We used a mixed effects logistic regression to analyze the probability that wasps
166 persisted for at least ten generations. This approach allowed us to examine statistically which
167 experimental treatments increased the probability of wasp persistence across generations. We
168 summed the number of replicate wasp populations that persisted for at least ten generations and
169 divided that by the number of total replicate simulations (n=100). Thus, each unique set of
170 experimental variables was associated with a single proportion describing wasp persistence. Our
171 mixed-effects model included all main effects and all possible two-way interactions between
172 variables (DF = 53). This provided an opportunity to test specific hypotheses about how
173 experimental treatments interacted to influence the probability of host-parasitoid persistence. We
174 removed one outlier from the model, which resulted in a total of 9599 observations. To correct
175 for overdispersion, we used an observation level random effect (OLRE). Based on residual
176 analysis using the DHARMA package for R statistical software (3.6.0), the model met all
177 assumptions of normality, heteroscedasticity, and overdispersion (Hartig 2019). The significance
178 of interactions was tested using type III analysis of deviance (e.g., Wald test). Post-hoc multiple
179 comparisons of the interactions were performed using the *emmeans* R package (Lenth 2019) and

180 P-values were adjusted using the Tukey method. All figures were generated using the *ggplot2* R
181 package (Wickham 2011).

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183 **SI Results**

184 **Observed vs. Simulated (Single generation host-parasitoid model)**

185 The intercept was significantly different from zero when modelling differences in fly
186 abundance ($\beta = 6.5$, $t = 14.4$, $P < 0.001$), revealing that simulated values were on average 6.5
187 individual flies fewer than what were observed in the experiment. Differences between observed
188 and simulated fly abundances were significantly impacted by temporal delay, resource
189 competition, and their interaction (Fig. S10A; Table S9). The underestimation of fly abundance
190 was highest at two and four days of temporal delay, both of which were significantly different
191 from the control treatments in low competition treatments (2-day estimate = 21.2, $t = 8.4$, $P <$
192 0.001 ; 4-day estimate = 10.5, $t = 5.4$, $p < 0.001$), but only a four-day delay showed significantly
193 differences in the high competition vials (4-day estimate = 10.6, $t = 5.5$, $P < 0.001$).

194 The intercept for the wasp abundance GLS was different from zero ($\beta = -1.03$, $t = -3.95$,
195 $P < 0.001$), indicating that the simulated values of wasp abundances were typically one
196 additional wasp than observed during the experiment (Fig S10B; Table S10). Observed and
197 simulated differences in wasp abundances were significantly from the control (0-day delay =
198 0.05) within the two-day (Estimate = -3.2, $t = -3.3$, $P = 0.02$) and four-day (Estimate = -1.2, $t = -3.4$,
199 $P = 0.01$) delay periods. A significant interaction between temperature and host species identified
200 that overestimation of wasp abundance with *D. birchii* was greater in 24°C than 28°C (Est=-0.68,
201 $t = -2.3$, $P = 0.04$), and more of an overestimation of wasp abundance from *D. sulfurigaster* in
202 28°C than 24°C (Est = 0.72, $t = 2.5$, $P = 0.03$).

227 **Fig. S1.** Observed and model predicted development times in vials without wasps (e.g., controls)
 228 across the four treatments for each unique species combination. Colored circles represent model
 229 predicted development times, while open grey circles display the observed mean development
 230 times of flies emerging from each vial. Development times differed significantly within a species
 231 for all pairwise comparisons except across competition treatments in 28°C for *D. birchii*
 232 (Estimate = 0.02, t-ratio = 1.3, P = 0.57) and between competition treatments in 24°C and 28°C
 233 for *D. Sulfurigaster* (Estimate = -0.04, t-ratio = -2.15, P = 0.14). P-values for multiple
 234 comparison were adjusted using the Tukey method.

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Fig. S2. Distribution of emerging adults across days in each temperature and competition treatment for A) *D. birchii*, B) *D. sulfurigaster*, and C) *Sulf-Bir*. Y-axis shows the proportion of all individuals reared in that condition that emerged on a given day, and the number within each

278 panel represents the total number of flies that were reared within a given treatment. The
279 horizontal panels are ordered from the upper to lower panel with 24C-High, 24C-Low, 28C-
280 High, and 28C-Low respectively. The dotted line represents the mean development time. Only
281 vials without a wasp were used.

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343 **Figure S3:** Observed and model predicted survival rates in vials without wasps (e.g., controls)
 344 across the four treatments for each species combination. Filled colored circles represent model
 345 predicted survival rates, while open grey circles display the observed proportion survival of flies
 346 emerging from each vial. Proportion survival, in the absence of wasps, did not differ
 347 significantly across a host species in 24 Celsius and high competition. Pairwise comparisons
 348 revealed that *D. birchii* survival was significantly lower than either of the other species
 349 combinations in 28-degree conditions. P-values for multiple comparison were adjusted using the
 350 Tukey method.

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Figure S4: Observed and model predicted survival rates in vials without wasps (e.g., controls) to identify differences in competitive ability among the two *Drosophila* species. Large filled colored circles represent model predicted survival rates, while smaller transparent circles display the observed proportion survival of flies emerging from each vial. Significant differences in the proportion of host survival are displayed as an asterisk and represents P-values < 0.05 in pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal means.

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Fig. S5. Mean abundances of each (A) wasp species and (B) fly species, and the observed values within each replicate. Mean fly abundance is averaged over both wasp species and over all three host species combinations for wasp abundance. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean (SEM). The x-axis shows the different temperature and resource competition treatments, ordered from slowest to fastest development times (phenological duration). Vertical columns

420 (Control, 0,2,4,6) represent the temporal delay between host and parasitoid, and control are
421 treatments without parasitoids.

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Fig S6: Estimated marginal means of proportion survival for the three fly species across phenological delay periods and temperatures. Marginal means were averaged across both levels of resource competition and wasp species. The effects of temporal delay on the probability of host survival varied with host species combinations and temperature, (ANOVA, $P = 0.078$). Even though *D. birchii* developed more quickly in elevated temperatures, wasps inflicted significantly more mortality on *D. birchii* across delay periods than either of the other two species combinations.

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Fig. S7: Estimated marginal means for host survival and successful parasitism for each unique host-parasitoid combination. Data were split accordingly and a mixed effects logistic regression with temperature, resource competition, and temporal delay and all respective two- and three-way interactions were modeled (DF = 10). Each panel shows (A) *D. birchii*, (B) *D. sulfurigaster*, and (C) *Sulf-Bir*. The two left vertical columns of figures show hosts interacting with *Asobara sp.* parasitoids, while the two right vertical panels display hosts interacting with *Ganaspis sp.* parasitoids. Within each figure, the top row displays the probability of host survival, while the bottom row shows the probability of successful parasitism. Notice that reductions in host survival do not always correspond to an increase in successful parasitism. No host-parasitoid species combination in isolation identified a significant three-way interaction among delay, temperature, and resource competition.

Fig S8: Boxplots and the observed proportion (color points) of replicated simulations ($n=100$) in which A) parasitoids averaged across host species, B) hosts averaged across host species, and C) hosts averaged across parasitoid species persisted for at least 10 generations. Each point represents a proportion out of 100 replicates runs within a given set of conditions ($n=9599$). All levels of relative host fecundity (1-10) and successful rate of wasp emergence (0.1-1) are included in this figure. Data is split across wasp species to help differentiate effects of phenological delay between the two wasp species. Predicted probabilities (not shown) of host-parasitoid persistence were less than 1%, but interspecific combinations of host species had significantly greater odds of persisting 10 generations than either species alone. Statistical analysis is provided in **SI Materials and Methods**. All effects were tested using Tukey's HSD test for multiple comparison.

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659 **Fig. S9.** Scatterplots showing the relationship between the relative fecundity (RF) of surviving
 660 host individuals and the proportion of replicate runs (n=100) in which the parasitoid persisted for
 661 at least ten generations within our parameterized host-parasitoid dynamic model. Each dot
 662 represents a proportion out of one-hundred and the replicated dots represent the different
 663 simulations under different RF values (2-10), temperature (24 and 28), competition level (high
 664 and low), and level of temporal delay (0,2,4,6 days). Lines were generated using the
 665 *geom_smooth loess* function in ggplot2 which plots smoothed conditional means between two
 666 continuous variables. Panel set A) shows patterns of wasp persistence on each host species, thus
 667 these smoothed conditional means are averaged over both wasp species. Panel set B) shows the
 668 proportions of wasps that persist at least ten generations for each separate wasp species and the
 669 conditional means are averaged over all three host species combinations.

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Fig. S10. Scatterplots showing the relationship between the percentage of adult parasitoids that survived into the next generation (SW) and the proportion of replicate runs (n=100) in which the parasitoid persisted for at least ten generations within our parameterized host-parasitoid dynamic model. Each dot represents a proportion out of one-hundred and the replicated dots represent the different simulations under each SW value (0.1-1), temperature (24 and 28), competition level (high and low), and level of temporal delay (0,2,4,6 days). Lines were generated using the *geom_smooth loess* function in *ggplot2* which plots smoothed conditional means between two continuous variables. Panel set A) shows patterns of wasp persistence on each host species, thus these smoothed conditional means are averaged over both wasp species. Panel set B) shows the proportions of wasps that persist at least ten generations for each separate wasp species and the conditional means are averaged over all three host species combinations.

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 729 **Fig S11:** Observed and model predicted differences between the observed and simulated values
 730 of (A) fly abundance and (B) wasp abundance from a generalized least squares analysis. Large
 731 colored circles represent model predicted differences and 95% confidence intervals, while
 732 smaller colored circles display the observed differences. Plots are arranged in this manner to help
 733 identify over and underestimating abundances of flies and wasps respectively. The dotted line
 734 represents situations in which our host-parasitoid model correctly identifies the number of flies
 735 or wasps that emerge from a given treatment. See **SI Methods and Results** for a more detailed
 736 explanation.

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761 **Table S1:** Type III analysis of deviance from a linear mixed effect model (LMER) for the
 762 development rate across different temperatures and levels of resource competition for each
 763 species combination. Block (n=5) was included as a random effect to account for any temporal
 764 differences across replicates. Residual degrees of freedom were calculated using the Kenward-
 765 Rodger degrees of freedom.
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Type III Wald F-tests with Kenward-Roger DF (KR.DF)

Source of variation	F	DF	KR.DF	P-value	
<i>Intercept</i>	14303.25	1	3.99	< 0.001	***
Species (SP)	456.45	2	105.51	< 0.001	***
Temperature (Temp)	762.45	1	105.02	< 0.001	***
Resource Competition (RC)	237.25	1	105.00	< 0.001	***
SP × Temp	5.57	2	105.01	0.005	**
SP × RC	26.49	2	105.00	< 0.001	***
Temp × RC	2.31	1	105.00	0.132	
SP × Temp × RC	0.62	2	105.00	0.541	

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795 **Table S2:** Summary of results from a linear mixed-effect model (LMER) for the development
796 rate across different temperatures and levels of resource competition for each species
797 combination. Estimates are on the log-scale. Values in bold represent significant effects. The
798 model's intercept corresponds to Species = *D. birchii*, Temp = 24 and Resource Competition =
799 High. *D. birchii*, 24C, and High competition serve as the reference levels for species,
800 temperatures, and resource competition respectively.
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<i>Predictors</i>	Response: log(Mean Dev. Time)		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>95% CI</i>	<i>p</i>
Intercept	2.59	2.55 – 2.64	<0.001
Species [Sulf.]	-0.2	-0.23 – -0.16	<0.001
Species [Sulf-Bir]	-0.11	-0.15 – -0.07	<0.001
Temp [28]	-0.19	-0.23 – -0.16	<0.001
Resource Competition (RC) [Low]	-0.06	-0.10 – -0.03	0.001
Species [Sulf] × Temp [28]	-0.02	-0.07 – 0.03	0.451
Species [Sulf-Bir] × Temp [28]	-0.05	-0.11 – -0.00	0.038
Species [Sulf] × RC [Low]	-0.11	-0.16 – -0.06	<0.001
Species [Sulf-Bir] × RC [Low]	-0.08	-0.13 – -0.03	0.002
Temp [28] × RC [Low]	0.04	-0.01 – 0.09	0.122
Species [Sulf] × Temp [28] × RC [Low]	-0.04	-0.11 – 0.03	0.282
Species [Sulf-Bir] × Temp [28] × RC [Low]	-0.01	-0.08 – 0.06	0.761
Random Effects			
σ^2	0		
$\tau_{00 \text{ Block}}$	0		
ICC	0.52		
N_{Block}	5		
Observations	121		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.888 / 0.946		

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813 **Table S3:** Type III analysis of deviance from a linear mixed effect model (LMER) for the
 814 standard deviation of development rate across different temperatures and levels of resource
 815 competition for each species combination. Residual degrees of freedom were calculated using
 816 the Kenward-Rodger degrees of freedom.
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Type III Wald F-tests with Kenward-Roger DF (KR.DF)

Source of variation	F	Df	KR.DF	Pr(>F)	
<i>Intercept</i>	0.017	1	93.754	0.897	
Species (SP)	27.572	2	104.667	0.000	***
Temperature (Temp)	21.224	1	103.025	0.000	***
Resource Competition (RC)	0.071	1	104.390	0.791	
Mean Dev. Time (MDT)	1.655	1	95.200	0.201	
SP × Temp	6.471	2	102.740	0.002	**
Species × Treatment	6.869	2	103.046	0.002	**
Temp × Treatment	4.073	1	102.398	0.046	*
Temp × MDT	24.411	1	103.408	0.000	***
SP × Temp × RC	3.225	2	102.303	0.044	*

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844 **Table S4:** Summary of results from a linear mixed-effect model (LMER) for the standard
845 deviation in development rate across different temperatures and levels of resource competition
846 for each species combination. Values in bold represent significant effects. The model's intercept
847 corresponds to Species = *D. birchii*, Temp = 24, Resource Competition = High, and mean
848 development time = 0. *D. birchii*, 24C, and High competition serve as the reference levels for
849 species, temperatures, and resource competition respectively.
850

<i>Predictors</i>	Response: SD Dev. Time		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>95% CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.09	-1.16 – 1.33	0.892
Species [Sulf]	0.21	-0.08 – 0.49	0.148
Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.7	0.48 – 0.93	<0.001
Temp [28]	-4.26	-6.08 – -2.43	<0.001
Resource Competiton (RC) [Low]	0.03	-0.17 – 0.22	0.79
MeanDevTime	0.06	-0.03 – 0.15	0.181
Species [Sulf] × Temp [28]	0.74	0.30 – 1.19	0.001
Species [Sulf-Bir] × Temp[28]	0.64	0.27 – 1.00	0.001
Species [Sulf] × RC [Low]	-0.42	-0.70 – -0.15	0.003
Species [Sulf-Bir] × RC [Low]	0.02	-0.25 – 0.29	0.87
Temp [28] × RC [Low]	0.27	0.01 – 0.54	0.046
Temp [28] × MeanDevTime	0.39	0.23 – 0.54	<0.001
Species [Sulf] × Temp [28] × RC [Low]	0.51	0.11 – 0.90	0.014
Species [Sulf-Bir] × Temp [28] × RC [Low]	0.33	-0.05 – 0.71	0.09
Random Effects			
σ^2	0.04		
τ_{00} Block	0.01		
ICC	0.19		
N_{Block}	5		
Observations	120		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.745 / 0.794		

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860 **Table S5:** Type III analysis of deviance from a mixed effect logistic regression (GLMER) for
 861 the proportion host survival across different temperatures and levels of resource competition for
 862 each species combination in the absence of parasitoids. Block (n=5) and an observation level
 863 random effects (vialID, n=121) were included as random effects to account for any temporal
 864 differences across replicates and correct for overdispersion within the model.
 865

Type III Wald χ^2 test

Source of variation	χ^2	DF	P-value	
<i>Intercept</i>	38.49	1	< 0.001	***
Species (SP)	62.40	2	< 0.001	***
Temperature (Temp)	97.48	1	< 0.001	***
Resource Competition (RC)	138.00	1	< 0.001	***
SP × Temp	29.46	2	< 0.001	***
SP × RC	12.21	2	0.002	**
Temp × RC	4.17	1	0.041	*
SP × Temp × RC	5.35	2	0.069	.

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895 **Table S6:** Summary of results from a linear mixed-effect model (LMER) for the mean in host
 896 survival rates different temperatures and levels of resource competition for each species
 897 combination. Values in bold represent significant effects. The model's intercept corresponds to
 898 Species = *D. birchii*, Temp = 24 and Resource Competition = High. *D. birchii*, 24C, and High
 899 competition serve as the reference levels for species, temperatures, and resource competition
 900 respectively.

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Response: Prop. Survival			
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Odds Ratios</i>	<i>95% CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	1.17	0.79 – 1.73	0.425
Species [Sulf]	1.17	0.68 – 2.02	0.569
Species [Sulf-Bir]	1.01	0.58 – 1.74	0.979
Temp [28]	0.23	0.13 – 0.39	<0.001
Resource Competition (RC) [Low]	4.5	2.58 – 7.86	<0.001
Species [Sulf] * Temp [28]	2.67	1.25 – 5.74	0.012
Species [Sulf-Bir] * Temp [28]	2.08	0.97 – 4.47	0.06
Species [Sulf] * RC [Low]	2.01	0.89 – 4.57	0.094
Species [Sulf-Bir] * RC [Low]	0.66	0.30 – 1.45	0.301
Temp [28] * RC [Low]	0.34	0.16 – 0.74	0.006
Species [Sulf] * Temp [28] * RC [Low]	1.69	0.55 – 5.18	0.359
Species [Sulf-Bir] * Temp [28] * RC [Low]	3.6	1.21 – 10.71	0.021
Random Effects			
σ^2	3.63		
τ_{00} vialID	0.34		
τ_{00} Block	0.01		
ICC	0		
N_{Block}	5		
N_{vialID}	121		
Observations	121		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.245 / 0.247		

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911 **Table S7:** Mean Abundance and proportion survival in control vials for each host species in
 912 intra- and interspecific combinations. Comp. represent the level of resource competition, while
 913 Comb. represents the intra- or interspecific combination of the two host species. SE shows the
 914 standard error of the mean for each observed average.
 915

Temp	Comp.	Species	Comb.	N	Abund.	SE	Surv.	SE
24	High	Birchii	Inter	10	22.20	2.33	0.44	0.05
24	High	Birchii	Intra	10	53.90	4.16	0.54	0.04
24	High	Sulfurigaster	Inter	10	32.20	2.29	0.64	0.05
24	High	Sulfurigaster	Intra	10	56.90	5.19	0.57	0.05
24	Low	Birchii	Inter	10	35.00	2.95	0.70	0.06
24	Low	Birchii	Intra	10	81.50	4.02	0.82	0.04
24	Low	Sulfurigaster	Inter	10	41.10	2.29	0.82	0.05
24	Low	Sulfurigaster	Intra	9	90.67	2.52	0.91	0.03
28	High	Birchii	Inter	10	10.20	2.20	0.20	0.04
28	High	Birchii	Intra	11	22.91	3.59	0.23	0.04
28	High	Sulfurigaster	Inter	10	26.80	2.82	0.54	0.06
28	High	Sulfurigaster	Intra	10	45.60	2.74	0.46	0.03
28	Low	Birchii	Inter	10	24.10	1.75	0.48	0.04
28	Low	Birchii	Intra	11	30.36	4.91	0.30	0.05
28	Low	Sulfurigaster	Inter	10	42.90	1.18	0.86	0.02
28	Low	Sulfurigaster	Intra	10	80.20	2.62	0.80	0.03

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937 **Table S8:** Post-hoc multiple comparison investigating effects of alternative species on host
938 survival between the two host species. Odds of survival were compared in the intraspecific and
939 interspecific treatments across each species, level of resource competition, and temperature. P-
940 values less than 0.05 were considered significant. “Inter” represents treatments where that
941 particular species was reared with the other species in the same vial, while “Intra” represents
942 treatments where that species was reared in isolation. OR represents the Odds ratio. Comp.
943 represents the level of resource competition, where High (2ml of food) and Low (20ml of food).
944 Temp. is the temperature that these vials were reared in. SE is the standard error of the mean. Df
945 is the degrees of freedom. All data in this analysis omitted vials where wasps were added.
946

Contrast	Host Species	Comp.	Temp	OR	SE	df	Z-ratio	P-value
Inter / Intra	<i>D. birchii</i>	High	24	0.661	0.187	Inf	-1.465	0.143
Inter / Intra	<i>D. sulfurigaster</i>	High	24	1.333	0.378	Inf	1.013	0.311
Inter / Intra	<i>D. birchii</i>	Low	24	0.482	0.141	Inf	-2.503	0.012 *
Inter / Intra	<i>D. sulfurigaster</i>	Low	24	0.414	0.130	Inf	-2.811	0.005 *
Inter / Intra	<i>D. birchii</i>	High	28	0.875	0.251	Inf	-0.467	0.641
Inter / Intra	<i>D. sulfurigaster</i>	High	28	1.363	0.385	Inf	1.097	0.273
Inter / Intra	<i>D. birchii</i>	Low	28	2.213	0.615	Inf	2.858	0.004 *
Inter / Intra	<i>D. sulfurigaster</i>	Low	28	1.471	0.438	Inf	1.297	0.195

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973 **Table S9:** Type III analysis of deviance from a mixed effect logistic regression (GLMM) for the
 974 proportion survival in the presence of delayed parasitoids. A likelihood ratio test (LRT) showed
 975 that removal of the three-way interaction did not significantly improve the model.
 976

Type III Wald χ^2 test

Source of variation	χ^2	Df	P-value	
<i>Intercept</i>	18.99	1	<0.001	***
Temperature (Temp)	1.05	1	0.31	
Resource Competition (RC)	45.38	1	<0.001	***
Delay (D)	871.69	3	<0.001	***
Species (SP)	93.22	2	<0.001	***
Wasp Species (WP)	43.20	1	<0.001	***
Temp \times RC	0.14	1	0.70	
Temp \times D	9.62	3	0.02	*
RC \times D	15.67	3	<0.001	**
Temp \times SP	56.61	2	<0.001	***
RC \times SP	4.48	2	0.11	
D \times SP	69.87	6	<0.001	***
D \times WP	33.26	3	<0.001	***
Temp \times RC \times D	3.92	3	0.27	
Temp \times D \times SP	14.98	6	0.02	*

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998 **Table S10:** Summary of results from a linear mixed-effect model (LMER) for the mean in host
999 survival rates in the presence of parasitoids. Values in bold represent significant effects. The
1000 model's intercept corresponds to Temp = 24, Treatment = High, Mismatch = 0, Species = *D.*
1001 *birchii* and WaspSpecies = *Asobara sp.* *D. birchii*, 24C, High competition, delay of 0 days, and
1002 *Asobara sp.* serve as the reference levels for species, temperatures, resource competition, delay,
1003 and wasp species respectively.

Response: Proportion Survival			
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Odds Ratios</i>	<i>95% CI</i>	<i>p</i>
Intercept	0.02	0.01 – 0.05	<0.001
Temp [28]	0.18	0.04 – 0.86	0.032
Resource Competition (RC) [Low]	1.5	0.61 – 3.72	0.38
Delay (D) [2]	13.15	4.12 – 42.00	<0.001
D [4]	183.79	57.28 – 589.70	<0.001
D [6]	43.37	13.75 – 136.84	<0.001
Species [Sulf]	0.65	0.22 – 1.94	0.446
Species [Sulf-Bir]	1.5	0.53 – 4.26	0.449
WaspSpecies (WSp) [Ganaspis]	0.43	0.23 – 0.80	0.008
Temp [28] * RC [Low]	2.06	0.57 – 7.43	0.269
Temp [28] * D [2]	6.35	0.96 – 41.83	0.055
Temp [28] * D [4]	0.75	0.11 – 4.86	0.759
Temp [28] * D [6]	2.99	0.47 – 19.13	0.248
RC [Low] * D [2]	3.76	1.28 – 11.08	0.016
RC [Low] * D [4]	1.43	0.49 – 4.16	0.511
RC [Low] * D [6]	1.71	0.59 – 4.97	0.324
Temp [28] * Species [Sulf]	7.64	1.42 – 41.19	0.018
Temp [28] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	2.76	0.51 – 14.96	0.238
RC [Low] * Species [Sulf]	1.45	0.75 – 2.80	0.266
RC [Low] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.73	0.39 – 1.38	0.33
D [2] * Species [Sulf]	0.68	0.18 – 2.55	0.567
D [4] * Species [Sulf]	1.77	0.47 – 6.67	0.399
D [6] * Species [Sulf]	9.61	2.60 – 35.56	0.001
D [2] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.55	0.15 – 2.01	0.368
D [4] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.5	0.14 – 1.82	0.295
D [6] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	2.05	0.57 – 7.37	0.274
D [2] * WSp [Ganaspis]	0.31	0.14 – 0.68	0.004
D [4] * WSp [Ganaspis]	1.15	0.52 – 2.57	0.726
D [6] * WSp [Ganaspis]	2.34	1.05 – 5.21	0.037
Temp [28] * RC [Low] * D [2]	0.47	0.09 – 2.40	0.367
Temp [28] * RC [Low] * D [4]	0.2	0.04 – 1.02	0.052
(Temp [28] * RC [Low]) * D [6]	0.39	0.08 – 1.96	0.251
Temp [28] * D [2] * Species [Sulf]	0.52	0.06 – 4.12	0.533
Temp [28] * D [4] * Species [Sulf]	12.02	1.46 – 98.83	0.021
Temp [28] * D [6] * Species [Sulf]	1.73	0.21 – 14.20	0.611
Temp [28] * D [2] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.66	0.08 – 5.34	0.701

Temp [28] * D [4] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	4	0.50 – 31.76	0.189
Temp [28] * D [6] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.61	0.08 – 4.80	0.641

Random Effects

σ^2	4.99
τ_{00} vialID	1.7
τ_{00} Block	0.14
ICC	0.03
N_{Block}	5
N_{vialID}	496
Observations	496
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.586 / 0.597

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1038 **Table S11:** Type III analysis of deviance from a mixed effect logistic regression (GLMER) for
 1039 the parasitism rate of delayed parasitoids. A likelihood ratio test (LRT) showed that keeping the
 1040 three-way interaction significantly improved the model.
 1041

Type III Wald χ^2 test

Source of variation	χ^2	DF	P-value	
(Intercept)	231.04	1	< 0.001	***
Temperature (T)	130.57	1	< 0.001	***
Resource Competition (RC)	1.39	1	0.238	
Delay (D)	342.29	3	< 0.001	***
Wasp Species (WP)	10.60	1	0.001	**
Species (SP)	5.80	2	0.055	.
T × RC	2.58	1	0.108	
T × D	3.19	3	0.363	
RC × D	3.07	3	0.381	
T × WP	45.62	1	< 0.001	***
RC × WP	37.96	1	< 0.001	***
D × WP	53.68	3	< 0.001	***
D × SP	24.02	6	0.001	***
T × SP	1.77	2	0.413	
T × RC × D	15.14	3	0.002	**
T × D × SP	11.84	6	0.066	.

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1063 **Table S12:** Summary of results from a linear mixed-effect model (LMER) for the mean
 1064 parasitism rates. Values in bold represent significant effects. The model's intercept corresponds
 1065 to Temp = 24, Treatment = High, Delay = 0, WaspSpecies = *Asobara* and Species = *D. birchii*.
 1066 *D. birchii*, 24C, High competition, Delay of 0 days, and *Asobara sp.* serve as the reference levels
 1067 for species, temperatures, resource competition respectively.
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<i>Predictors</i>	Response: Parasitism Rate		
	<i>Odds Ratios</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	3.13	1.53 – 6.42	0.002
Temp [28]	0.07	0.03 – 0.19	<0.001
Resource Competition (RC) [Low]	0.66	0.36 – 1.22	0.187
Delay (D) [2]	0.21	0.09 – 0.50	<0.001
D [4]	0.01	0.01 – 0.03	<0.001
D [6]	0.01	0.00 – 0.03	<0.001
Wasp Species (WSp) [Ganaspis]	0.18	0.10 – 0.31	<0.001
Species [Sulf]	0.51	0.26 – 1.01	0.055
Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.64	0.33 – 1.25	0.194
Temp [28] * RC [Low]	0.73	0.31 – 1.74	0.483
Temp [28] * D [2]	3.05	0.80 – 11.59	0.102
Temp [28] * D [4]	2.17	0.35 – 13.61	0.409
Temp [28] * D [6]	1.19	0.09 – 14.99	0.892
RC [Low] * D [2]	1.06	0.49 – 2.31	0.876
RC [Low] * D [4]	0.54	0.23 – 1.27	0.159
RC [Low] * D [6]	0.26	0.10 – 0.67	0.005
Temp [28] * WSp [Ganaspis]	0.15	0.09 – 0.26	<0.001
RC [Low] * WSp [Ganaspis]	4.94	2.97 – 8.22	<0.001
D [2] * WSp [Ganaspis]	2.49	1.35 – 4.59	0.004
D [4] * WSp [Ganaspis]	11.74	5.70 – 24.18	<0.001
D [6] * WSp [Ganaspis]	8.11	3.53 – 18.65	<0.001
D [2] * Species [Sulf]	2.84	1.10 – 7.31	0.031
D [4] * Species [Sulf]	0.46	0.16 – 1.38	0.167
D [6] * Species [Sulf]	0.65	0.21 – 2.01	0.451
D [2] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	1.93	0.75 – 4.99	0.172
D [4] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	1.67	0.61 – 4.55	0.317
D [6] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.92	0.30 – 2.82	0.885
Temp [28] * Species [Sulf]	11.39	3.86 – 33.55	<0.001
Temp [28] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	5.62	1.91 – 16.57	0.002
Temp [28] * RC [Low] * D [2]	0.4	0.12 – 1.37	0.145
Temp [28] * RC [Low] * D [4]	6.25	1.07 – 36.56	0.042
Temp [28] * RC [Low] * D [6]	18.26	1.43 – 233.43	0.025
Temp [28] * D [2] * Species [Sulf]	0.13	0.03 – 0.61	0.01
Temp [28] * D [4] * Species [Sulf]	0.08	0.01 – 0.66	0.019
Temp [28] * D [6] * Species [Sulf]	0.04	0.00 – 0.72	0.029
Temp [28] * D [2] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.26	0.05 – 1.24	0.091
Temp [28] * D [4] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.13	0.02 – 0.87	0.035

Temp [28] * D [6] * Species [Sulf-Bir]	0.17	0.02 – 1.69	0.131
Random Effects			
σ^2	4.43		
τ_{00} vialID	1.14		
τ_{00} Block	0.17		
ICC	0.04		
N_{Block}	5		
N_{vialID}	496		
Observations	496		
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.568 / 0.583		

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1105 **Table S13:** Post-hoc multiple comparison investigating effects of alternative species on host
 1106 survival across phenological delays, temperatures, and resource competition. Odds of survival
 1107 were compared across resource levels and temperatures to examine whether alternative host
 1108 species dampen differences across treatments. P-values less than 0.05 were considered
 1109 significant. OR represents the Odds ratio. Comp. represents the level of resource competition,
 1110 where High (2ml of food) and Low (20ml of food). Temp. is the temperature that these vials
 1111 were reared in. SE is the standard error of the mean. df is the degrees of freedom.
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Contrast	Species	Delay	OR	SE	df	Z-ratio	P-value	
High / Low	D. birchii	0	0.464	0.182	Inf	-1.961	0.050	*
High / Low	D. birchii	2	0.179	0.058	Inf	-5.354	<0.001	*
High / Low	D. birchii	4	0.726	0.233	Inf	-0.997	0.319	
High / Low	D. birchii	6	0.437	0.138	Inf	-2.630	0.009	*
24 / 28	D. birchii	0	3.894	2.689	Inf	1.969	0.049	*
24 / 28	D. birchii	2	0.891	0.398	Inf	-0.259	0.796	
24 / 28	D. birchii	4	11.695	5.225	Inf	5.504	<0.001	*
24 / 28	D. birchii	6	2.100	0.895	Inf	1.740	0.082	
High / Low	D. sulfurigaster	0	0.319	0.119	Inf	-3.068	0.002	*
High / Low	D. sulfurigaster	2	0.123	0.039	Inf	-6.583	<0.001	*
High / Low	D. sulfurigaster	4	0.500	0.163	Inf	-2.129	0.033	*
High / Low	D. sulfurigaster	6	0.301	0.099	Inf	-3.667	<0.001	*
24 / 28	D. sulfurigaster	0	0.509	0.267	Inf	-1.286	0.198	
24 / 28	D. sulfurigaster	2	0.226	0.098	Inf	-3.444	0.001	*
24 / 28	D. sulfurigaster	4	0.127	0.060	Inf	-4.385	<0.001	*
24 / 28	D. sulfurigaster	6	0.159	0.078	Inf	-3.770	<0.001	*
High / Low	Sulf-Bir	0	0.637	0.236	Inf	-1.217	0.224	
High / Low	Sulf-Bir	2	0.246	0.078	Inf	-4.449	<0.001	*
High / Low	Sulf-Bir	4	0.997	0.309	Inf	-0.010	0.992	
High / Low	Sulf-Bir	6	0.600	0.187	Inf	-1.643	0.100	
24 / 28	Sulf-Bir	0	1.409	0.744	Inf	0.650	0.516	
24 / 28	Sulf-Bir	2	0.485	0.212	Inf	-1.658	0.097	
24 / 28	Sulf-Bir	4	1.057	0.442	Inf	0.132	0.895	
24 / 28	Sulf-Bir	6	1.241	0.527	Inf	0.508	0.611	

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1122 **Table S14:** Type III analysis of deviance from a mixed effect logistic regression (GLMM) for
 1123 the proportion of replicate simulations in which wasps persisted for at least 10 generations. A
 1124 total of 9599 observations were used in the model with 53 degrees of freedom. An observation
 1125 level random effect (OLRE) was used to help correct for overdispersion in the logistic
 1126 regression. Intraclass correlation (ICC) for the OLRE = 0.47.

Type III Wald χ^2 tests

Source of variation	χ^2	DF	P-value	
<i>Intercept</i>	1111.705	1	< 0.001	***
Species (SP)	11.570	2	0.003	**
Wasp Species (WP)	0.071	1	0.790	
Temperature (Temp)	262.691	1	< 0.001	***
Resource Competition (RC)	159.682	1	< 0.001	***
Delay (D)	346.997	3	< 0.001	***
Relative Fecundity (RF)	69.026	1	< 0.001	***
Survival wasps (SW)	23.015	1	< 0.001	***
SP \times WP	63.399	2	< 0.001	***
SP \times Temp	173.916	2	< 0.001	***
SP \times RC	1.308	2	0.520	
SP \times D	132.660	6	< 0.001	***
SP \times RF	14.821	2	0.001	***
SP \times SW	31.951	2	< 0.001	***
WP \times Temp	6.468	1	0.011	*
WP \times RC	8.187	1	0.004	**
WP \times D	290.206	3	< 0.001	***
WP \times RF	0.292	1	0.589	
WP \times SW	0.432	1	0.511	
Temp \times RC	52.485	1	< 0.001	***
Temp \times D	538.369	3	< 0.001	***
Temp \times RF	21.977	1	< 0.001	***
Temp \times SW	164.127	1	< 0.001	***
RC \times D	172.805	3	< 0.001	***
RC \times RF	11.773	1	0.001	***
RC \times SW	68.949	1	< 0.001	***
D \times RF	9.584	3	0.022	*
D \times SW	337.235	3	< 0.001	***
RF \times SW	1.332	1	0.248	

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1131 **Table S15:** Type 3 analysis of deviance for the generalized least squared model on difference
 1132 between the observed and simulated values of fly abundance. GLS was used to account to
 1133 heteroskedastic residuals. Residual degrees of freedom = 106. 120 observations. 19 degrees of
 1134 freedom, including the identity matrix (random effect in GLS).
 1135

Analysis of Deviance Table (Type III tests)

Source of variation	DF	χ^2	P-value	
<i>Intercept</i>	1	208.23	< 0.001	***
Temperature (Temp)	1	0.58	0.447	
Delay (D)	4	115.98	< 0.001	***
Resource Competition (RC)	1	16.16	< 0.001	***
Species (SP)	2	3.74	0.154	
Wasp Species (WP)	1	0.57	0.449	
D × RC	4	22.67	< 0.001	***

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1166 **Table S16:** Likelihood ratio test (LRT) for the GLS model on differences between observed and
 1167 simulated values of wasp abundance. Total degrees of freedom (observations) = 96, 85 residual
 1168 degrees of freedom. 19 degrees of freedom including the identity matrix (random effect in GLS).
 1169 Model: Difference Observed/Simulated ~ Temp + Delay + RC + Species + Wasp Species +
 1170 (Temp × Species)
 1171

Likelihood ratio test

Source of variation	DF	AIC	LRT	P-value	
<none>		412			
Delay	3	425	19.11	0.00026	***
Resource Competition	1	411	1.02	0.31235	
Wasp Species	1	410	0.01	0.92074	
Temperature × Species	2	420	11.95	0.00254	**

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1203 **Dataset S1 (separate file; all.dat.sbNov24.csv).** Data that provides survival and parasitism
1204 rates for each individual vial. Importantly, this data combines survival rates from the *D.*
1205 *sulfurigaster-D. birchii* combined host treatment into a single value within a vial. This data was
1206 used for all analyses.

1207 **Dataset S2 (separate file; mean.sim.obs2Jun292020.csv).** Data that compares the mean
1208 values for the observed and simulated data from the single generation host-parasitoid model
1209 developed in this manuscript. This was used to examine differences simulated and observed
1210 values in host and parasitoid abundance after a single generation experiment.

1211 **Dataset S3 (separate file; TABHISTOG.csv).** Data from dynamic simulation model that is
1212 summarized across the 100 replicate population runs for each unique set of treatments. We
1213 used these data to investigate the proportion of replicates that persisted for at least 10
1214 generations (variable: P10prop).

1215 **Dataset S4 (separate file; param.table.June17.csv).** Data that provides parameters such as:
1216 em = estimated mortality of flies (total mortality), vm = variance of the em, ea = estimated
1217 mortality due to competition, va = variance of ea, ep = estimated death due to parasitism, vp =
1218 variance of ep, H0 = initial number of fly larvae that we start with in this simulation, R = the
1219 volume of food (in our case 2 or 20ml), Time = the number of days that wasps could have an
1220 impact on host mortality, which in our case is 8 days (0-8days), w = Delay window, w also
1221 includes the control vials without a wasp. w=0 is the control, w=1 is Delay 0, w=2 is Delay 2,
1222 w=3 is Delay 4, w=4 is Delay 6, d is the correction of wasp abundances. Our model
1223 overestimated parasitoid abundances and therefore we had to add additional parasitoid
1224 mortality through this variable. These data were then inserted in the single generation model to
1225 get expected abundances of flies and parasitoids.

1226 **Dataset S5 (separate file; all.dat.nsbNov24.csv).** Data that provides survival and parasitism
1227 rates for each individual vial. Importantly, this data does not combine survival rates from the *D.*
1228 *sulfurigaster-D. birchii* combined host treatment into a single value within a vial. This data was
1229 used for analyses that investigated competition between the two host species.

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1248 **Supplementary files:**
1249
1250 **R-code S1 (separate file; PublicationDevtimeMay112021.R).** R-code used to calculate
1251 development times in control treatments.
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1253 **R-code S2 (separate file; PublicationVarianceDevTime.R).** R-code used to calculate and plot
1254 variance in host development times in control treatments.
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1256 **R-code S3 (separate file; PublicationPropHostSurvContMay112021.R).** R-code used to
1257 calculate proportion survival for flies in control treatment.
1258
1259 **R-code S4 (separate file; PublicationPropSurv3FactorMay112021.R).** R-code used to model
1260 proportion survival for flies when in the presence of parasitoids.
1261
1262 **R-code S5 (separate file; PublicationPsitRateFactorMay112021.R).** R-code used to model
1263 parasitism rates
1264
1265 **R-code S6 (separate file; parameter.estimatesMay19.R).** R-code used to acquire estimates:
1266 em = estimated mortality of flies (total mortality), vm = variance of the em, ea = estimated
1267 mortality due to competition, va = variance of ea, ep = estimated death due to parasitism, vp =
1268 variance of ep, H0 = initial number of fly larvae that we start with in this simulation, R = the
1269 volume of food (in our case 2 or 20ml), Time = the number of days that wasps could have an
1270 impact on host mortality, which in our case is 8 days (0-8days), w = Delay window, w also
1271 includes the control vials without a wasp. w=0 is the control, w=1 is Delay 0, w=2 is Delay 2,
1272 w=3 is Delay 4, w=4 is Delay 6, d is the correction of wasp abundances. This R-code will
1273 generate the param.table.June17.csv.
1274
1275 **R-code S7 (separate file; PublicationObsSimMAY112021.R).** R-code used to compare the
1276 observed and simulated fly and parasitoid abundance within a single generation experiment.
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1278 **R-code S8 (separate file; PublicationDynamicAnalMay112021.R).** R-code uses the
1279 summarized dynamic model data and statistically analyzes probability that on host and
1280 parasitoid will persist.
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1283 **Matlab-code S1 (separate file; matlab_codes.zip).** Matlab code was used to perform the
1284 dynamic model to investigate host and parasitoid persistence across 100 generations. Each part
1285 is commented with an explanatory readme.txt file.
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Model, parameterization & simulations

Supplement for “Effects of phenological mismatch under warming are modified by community context”

N. A. Pardikes, T.A. Revilla, C-H. Lue, M. Thierry, D. Souto, and J. Hrcek

This supplement describes the model, parameterization and simulation protocols applied to single generation experimental data on host–parasitoid interactions. All experiments are started with the same initial number of hosts, $H_0 = 100$. In the case of mixed hosts 50 eggs of both species are used so that the initial number is also 100. Let H_T be the recorded number of surviving hosts emerging as adults from day $T = 8$ until the finalization of the experiment. Unless explicitly stated, the following notation is used to label the experimental conditions:

- Low or high temperature denoted $\theta = 0$ (24 °C) or $\theta = 1$ (28 °C) respectively
- Low or high competition denoted $\gamma = 0$ (20 ml food) or $\gamma = 1$ (2 ml food) respectively
- Occurrence of parasitism denoted by $\omega = 0$ (never), 1 (days 1–2), 2 (3–4), 3 (5–6) or 4 (6–8).

Parasitoids are introduced on day $\tau = 0, 2, 4$ or 6 and removed $h = 2$ days later. So, parasitism never happens ($\omega = 0$) or happens during one of four time windows ($\omega = 1, 2, 3, 4$) within the first $T = 8$ days of the experiment. The number of introduced parasitoids is $W = 3$ female individuals, plus 3 non-parasitising adults needed for mating.

1 Mathematical model

1.1 Dynamics within generations

Let H_t and I_t be the number of non-parasitised and parasitised hosts on day t , respectively. A day later

$$H_{t+1} = H_t e^{-M} e^{-P(t)} \quad \text{where: } H_0 > 0 \quad (1)$$

$$I_{t+1} = H_t e^{-M} \left(1 - e^{-P(t)}\right) e^{-d} + I_t e^{-M} \quad \text{where: } I_0 = 0. \quad (2)$$

where M is host mortality and $P(t)$ is the parasitoid attack rate of day t , and $e = 2.71828\dots$ is the base of natural logarithms. Equation (1) gives the number of hosts escaping death and parasitism. Equation (2) gives the number of infested hosts and consists of two parts: the first accounts for newly infected hosts, the second accounts for previously infected hosts. Parasitoid handling causes additional mortality d to infested hosts. e.g., injuries. The iteration of system (1,2) starts with $H_0 = 100$ eggs and $I_0 = 0$ on day $t = 0$. Mortality and attack rates are modeled by

$$M = m_\theta + a_\theta \frac{H_0}{R_\gamma} \quad (3)$$

$$P(t) = p_{\theta\gamma\omega} \phi_\omega(t), \quad (4)$$

where a_θ is a temperature-dependent coefficient that relates mortality with host per resource density. Although hosts and resources decline with time, the experiments don't record these levels between days $t = 0$ and $T = 8$. Thus, we assume that resource competition depends on initial data, i.e.,

$H_0 = 100$ eggs divided by the initial resource level $R_\gamma = 20$ or 2 ml food. M is independent of time, but dependent on the experiment's temperature (θ) and resource level (γ). In the absence of competition and parasitism hosts die with temperature-dependent intrinsic rate m_θ .

Hosts turn infected in proportion to female parasitoid density $p_{\theta\gamma\omega} = k_{\theta\gamma\omega}W$. This occurs when t falls within the corresponding attack window ω , i.e.,

$$\phi_\omega(t) \begin{cases} = 1 & \text{if } 2(\omega - 1) \leq t < 2\omega \\ = 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

This allows us to model the effect of parasitoid attack (a)synchrony. Note that when $\omega = 0$, $\phi_0(t)$ defaults to zero because $2(\omega - 1) = -2$ and but $t \geq 0$. Thus (5) already considers experiments without parasitoid. The specific attack rate $k_{\theta\gamma\omega} = p_{\theta\gamma\omega}/W$ depends on temperature, resource level, and attack window of the experiment.

Since attack windows last $h = 2$ days, system (1,2) can be iterated to project the number of non-parasitised & parasitised hosts in day $T = 8$:

$$H_T = H_0 e^{-MT - 2kW} \quad (6)$$

$$I_T = H_0 e^{-MT - d}(1 - e^{-2kW}) \quad (7)$$

where $k = k_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ depends on temperature, food level and invasion window. Note that if $W = 0$ equation (6) turns into $H_T = H_0 e^{-MT}$, geometric decay in the absence of parasitoids, an experimental condition that is convenient for calculating components of M (3). All the parameters needed to run model equations (6,7) can be estimated using experimental counts of adult hosts and wasps emergence.

1.2 Dynamics between generations

Given an initial number of eggs H_0 and wasps W , the system formed by equations (1,2) is iterated T time units (e.g., 8 days like in the experiment) to obtain the number of surviving non-parasitised H_T and parasitised hosts I_T . The initial number of eggs and wasps for the next generation is projected by the following equations

$$H'_0 = H_T(H_0, W) \times R_F \quad (8)$$

$$W' = I_T(H_0, W) \times 0.5 \times S_W. \quad (9)$$

where R_F is the net reproductive rate of the hosts, i.e., the expected number of new offspring per generation, and S_W is the survival rate of adult wasps emerging from parasitised hosts. The 0.5 factor in (9) indicates that only female parasitoids attack hosts, at 50:50 female:male sex ratio. Parameter R_F condenses all influences on host fertility and survival beyond the phase governed by system (1,2). Host viability requires that $R_F > 1$. Parameter $0 \leq S_W \leq 1$ comprises factors affecting the survival probability of female wasps. Model (8,9) assumes non-overlapping host and parasitoid generations.

2 Parameter estimation

From equation (1), the number of non-infected hosts in day T is

$$H_T = H_0 e^{-\mu T}, \quad (10)$$

where $\mu = \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} M + P(t)$ is the combined rate of decrease for T days. Since M is constant, but $P(t) > 0$ only $h = 2$ days and zero otherwise, we have

$$\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega} = - \left(m_\theta + a_\theta \frac{H_0}{R} + \frac{h}{T} p_{\theta\gamma\omega} \right) T. \quad (11)$$

where $p_{\theta\gamma\omega} = k_{\theta\gamma\omega}W$ ($\theta\gamma\omega$ specifies the experimental conditions). According to (10) $\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ can be calculated using

$$\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega} = \frac{1}{T} \ln \left(\frac{H_0}{H_T} \right)_{\theta\gamma\omega} \approx \frac{2.3026}{T} \log_{10} \left(\frac{H_0}{H_T} \right)_{\theta\gamma\omega}, \quad (12)$$

by setting H_T to the number of adult flies recorded from day $T = 8$ and beyond, on the basis that the number non parasitised hosts surviving up to day T can't be lower than the actual number of adult flies recorded. A small fraction of the experiments results in total parasitism, i.e., $H_T = 0$, in these cases we set $H_T = 1$ in order to perform calculations. This means that the maximum mortality rate is capped at $\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega} \approx 0.576$. Thus $\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ overestimates real pre-adult mortality rates, which we can't be directly measured. The rest of this section shows how to obtain m_θ, a_θ and $p_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ by comparing the $\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ between experiments.

Calculation of m_θ and a_θ at temperature θ uses experiments without parasitoids ($\omega = 0$), by comparing mortality between food level $\gamma_0 = 20$ ml ($\theta 00$) and $\gamma_1 = 2$ ml ($\theta 10$). Setting $p_{\theta\gamma_0} = 0$ in (11) we obtain two equations

$$\mu_{\theta 00} = m_\theta + a_\theta H_0 / R_0 \quad (13)$$

$$\mu_{\theta 10} = m_\theta + a_\theta H_0 / R_1, \quad (14)$$

one for 20 ml of food (13) and the other for 2 ml (14). Solving for m_θ and a_θ we get

$$m_\theta = \frac{R_0 R_1}{R_0 - R_1} \left(\frac{\mu_{\theta 00}}{R_1} - \frac{\mu_{\theta 10}}{R_0} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$a_\theta = \frac{R_0 R_1 (\mu_{\theta 10} - \mu_{\theta 00})}{H_0 (R_0 - R_1)}. \quad (16)$$

Next we set $\mu_{\theta\gamma_0} = m_\theta + a_\theta H_0 / R_\gamma$ in (11). Solving for $p_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ gives

$$p_{\theta\gamma\omega} = \frac{T(\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega} - \mu_{\theta\gamma_0})}{h}, \quad (17)$$

where $\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ is the experimental host mortality with parasitoids during interaction window ω , and $\mu_{\theta\gamma_0}$ is the corresponding mortality without parasitoids (same temperature & food level).

The linearity of (15,16,17), plus the fact that $\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ and $\mu_{\theta\gamma_0}$ do not co-vary (they come from independent experiments), allows the derivation of expected values and variances of m_θ, a_θ and $p_{\theta\gamma\omega}$. The following list shows them and their corresponding estimators on the right:

$$E[m_\theta] = \frac{R_0 E[\mu_{\theta 00}] - R_1 E[\mu_{\theta 10}]}{R_0 - R_1} \quad \hat{m}_\theta = \frac{R_0 \bar{\mu}_{\theta 00} - R_1 \bar{\mu}_{\theta 10}}{R_0 - R_1} \quad (18)$$

$$V[m_\theta] = \frac{R_0^2 V[\mu_{\theta 00}] + R_1^2 V[\mu_{\theta 10}]}{(R_0 - R_1)^2} \quad \hat{\sigma}_{m_\theta}^2 = \frac{R_0^2 s_{\theta 00}^2 + R_1^2 s_{\theta 10}^2}{(R_0 - R_1)^2} \quad (19)$$

$$E[a_\theta] = \frac{R_0 R_1 \{E[\mu_{\theta 10}] - E[\mu_{\theta 00}]\}}{H_0 (R_0 - R_1)} \quad \hat{a}_\theta = \frac{R_0 R_1 (\bar{\mu}_{\theta 10} - \bar{\mu}_{\theta 00})}{H_0 (R_0 - R_1)} \quad (20)$$

$$V[a_\theta] = \left(\frac{R_0 R_1}{R_0 - R_1} \right)^2 \frac{V[\mu_{\theta 10}] + V[\mu_{\theta 00}]}{H_0^2} \quad \hat{\sigma}_{a_\theta}^2 = \left(\frac{R_0 R_1}{H_0 (R_0 - R_1)} \right)^2 (s_{\theta 10}^2 + s_{\theta 00}^2) \quad (21)$$

$$E[p_{\theta\gamma\omega}] = \frac{T \{E[\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}] - E[\mu_{\theta\gamma_0}]\}}{h} \quad \hat{p}_{\theta\gamma\omega} = \frac{T(\bar{\mu}_{\theta\gamma\omega} - \bar{\mu}_{\theta\gamma_0})}{h} \quad (22)$$

$$V[p_{\theta\gamma\omega}] = \frac{T^2 \{V[\mu_{\theta\gamma\omega}] + V[\mu_{\theta\gamma_0}]\}}{h^2} \quad \hat{\sigma}_{p_{\theta\gamma\omega}}^2 = \left(\frac{T}{h} \right)^2 (s_{\theta\gamma\omega}^2 + s_{\theta\gamma_0}^2), \quad (23)$$

where sample means and sample variances replace $E[\mu]$ and $V[\mu]$ from the left. Given $H_0 = 100$ eggs, $R_0 = 20, R_1 = 2$ ml & $T = 8, h = 2$ days, the formulas from the right simplify to:

$$\begin{aligned} m_\theta &= \frac{10 \times \bar{\mu}_{\theta 00} - \bar{\mu}_{\theta 10}}{9} & a_\theta &= \frac{\bar{\mu}_{\theta 10} - \bar{\mu}_{\theta 00}}{45} & p_{\theta\gamma\omega} &= 4(\bar{\mu}_{\theta\gamma\omega} - \bar{\mu}_{\theta\gamma_0}) \\ \sigma_{m_\theta}^2 &= \frac{100 \times s_{\theta 00}^2 + s_{\theta 10}^2}{81} & \sigma_{a_\theta}^2 &= \frac{s_{\theta 00}^2 + s_{\theta 10}^2}{2025} & \sigma_{p_{\theta\gamma\omega}}^2 &= 16(s_{\theta\gamma\omega}^2 + s_{\theta\gamma_0}^2), \end{aligned}$$

with carets ($\hat{}$) removed for notational economy.

We are left with parameter d , i.e., handling mortality in equation (2). From equation (7) we obtain

$$d = \ln \left(\frac{H_0 e^{-MT}}{I_T} \right) + \ln \left(1 - e^{-2kW} \right),$$

but to estimate the $d_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ of a particular experiment we use instead

$$d_{\theta\gamma\omega} = \max \left[0, \ln \left(\frac{\overline{FLY}_{\theta\gamma 0}}{\overline{WSP}_{\theta\gamma\omega}} \right) + \ln(1 - e^{-2p_{\theta\gamma\omega}}) \right], \quad (24)$$

where $\overline{WSP}_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ is the average number of wasps emerging for attack window $\omega = 1, 2, 3, 4$, and $\overline{FLY}_{\theta\gamma 0}$ the average number of flies emerging from corresponding experiment without parasitoids. Both \overline{WSP} and \overline{FLY} must be positive. Thus, for experiments without a single emergence the average is set to $\frac{1}{\# \text{replicates}}$, i.e., assume that at least one replicate produces a new wasp or fly. Generally $\overline{FLY}_{\theta\gamma 0} > \overline{WSP}_{\theta\gamma\omega}$ so the first term of (24) is positive. The second term is (generally) negative because $e^{-2p_{\theta\gamma\omega}} < 1$, thus the maximum operator ensures non-negative results. There is no reliable way to derive expectations and variances for $d_{\theta\gamma\omega}$.

3 Simulations

Here we describe stochastic simulation protocols, within generations and across generations. For ease of presentation we drop $\theta\gamma\omega$ indicators (implicit assumption of experimental conditions).

3.1 Single generation

Single generation simulations run $T = 8$ days. To simulate environmental stochasticity m, a and p are sampled daily, from normal distributions with means and variances set to their estimators in equations (18–23), i.e.,

$$m \sim \mathcal{N}(m, \sigma_m), \quad a \sim \mathcal{N}(a, \sigma_a), \quad p \sim \mathcal{N}(p, \sigma_p). \quad (25)$$

Next, the format of equations (1,2) indicates that for H_t and I_t , the number of non-parasitised and parasitised hosts in day $t + 1$ are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} H_{t+1} &= X_t \\ I_{t+1} &= Y_t + Z_t, \end{aligned}$$

where X_t and Y_t are sampled from the trinomial distribution

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_t \\ Y_t \\ H_t - X_t - Y_t \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{M} \left(H_t \left| \begin{bmatrix} e^{-M-P(t)} \\ e^{-M-d}(1 - e^{-P(t)}) \\ 1 - e^{-M-P(t)} - e^{-M-d}(1 - e^{-P(t)}) \end{bmatrix} \right. \right), \quad (26)$$

and Z_t from the binomial distribution

$$Z_t \sim \mathcal{B}(I_t | e^{-M}), \quad (27)$$

where $M = m + aH/R$ and $P(t) = p\phi(t)$ according to equations (3,4), making use of the normal sampling corresponding to day t . Thus, the demographic projection from one day to the next features environmental and demographic stochasticity around the deterministic skeleton of model (1,2). Notice that before, after or in absence the host–parasitoid interaction window, the sampling in (26) defaults to binomial.

By setting $H_0 = 100$ eggs and $W = 3$ wasps, the outcome of a large number of replicates, e.g., 100, can be compared with the distribution of emerging flies and wasps in corresponding experiments. Keep in mind that parameter d is not sampled because we do not have a reliable estimator for its variance.

3.2 Multiple generations

Multiple generations are simulated by continuation of single generation simulations. Like in the experiments, these start with $H_0 = 100$ eggs and $W = 3$ wasps in generation 0, but subsequent generations update these values using equations (8) and (9) respectively.

For each host–parasitoid pair and experimental condition, i.e., temperature, food level, attack window ($\theta\gamma\omega$), the dynamics is projected 100 generations for $R_F = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10\}$ and $S_W = \{\frac{1}{10}, \frac{2}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{4}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{7}{10}, \frac{8}{10}, \frac{9}{10}, 1\}$. Each (R_F, S_W) pair of this 10×10 grid is replicated 100 times. Thus, the total number of replicates is 10000. The entire 101 days time series (generations 0, 1, . . . , 100) of hosts and parasitoids of each replicate is recorded for statistical analyses of host and parasitoid persistence.

The simulations were performed in Matlab R2017a. Figures 1 to 4 below illustrate interaction dynamics between *Birchii* and *Asobara* for 24 °C and 20 ml of food, at different levels of temporal mismatch/delay (Fig.1: 0 days, Fig.2: 2 days, Fig.3: 4 days, Fig.4: 6 days). Notice that many $R_F \times S_F$ combinations cause extinction because for different reasons:

- overexploiting hosts up to extinction on the first generations (e.g., right side of Figs. 1a and 1b)
- low parasitoid fitness (e.g., left side of Fig. 1b or 3b)
- extreme oscillations (e.g., left side of Fig. 2b)

Keep in mind that Figures 1 to 4 do not capture all the dynamic complexity arising from all six different host–parasitoid combinations.

(a) host timeseries

(b) parasitoid timeseries

Figure 1: (a) Host/fly (*Birchii*) and (b) parasitoid/wasp (*Asobara*) dynamics. There are 100 timeseries (different colors) for each combination of host reproductive rate (R_F) and adult parasitoid survival (S_W). Temperature: 24 °C, food level: 20 ml, mismatch: 0 days ($\omega = 1$).

Figure 2: (a) Host/fly (*Birchii*) and (b) parasitoid/wasp (*Asobara*) dynamics. There are 100 timeseries (different colors) for each combination of host reproductive rate (R_F) and adult parasitoid survival (S_W). Temperature: 24 °C, food level: 20 ml, mismatch: 2 days ($\omega = 2$).

(a) host timeseries

(b) parasitoid timeseries

Figure 3: (a) Host/fly (*Birchii*) and (b) parasitoid/wasp (*Asobara*) dynamics. There are 100 timeseries (different colors) for each combination of host reproductive rate (R_F) and adult parasitoid survival (S_W). Temperature: 24 °C, food level: 20 ml, mismatch: 4 days ($\omega = 3$).

(a) host timeseries

(b) parasitoid timeseries

Figure 4: (a) Host/fly (*Birchii*) and (b) parasitoid/wasp (*Asobara*) dynamics. There are 100 timeseries (different colors) for each combination of host reproductive rate (R_F) and adult parasitoid survival (S_W). Temperature: 24 °C, food level: 20 ml, mismatch: 6 days ($\omega = 4$).